

Framing a sustainability agenda for Digital Out of Home Advertising in Indian Smart Cities

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Abstract

Indian Smart Cities Mission has positioned urban sustainability as a key developmental priority, yet the role of Digital Out of Home advertising in promoting this vision remains underexplored. By taking an ecosystem approach, this chapter looked at how Digital Out of Home advertising in smart cities are interdependent on other social systems and urban imaginaries. It specifically looked at how the narrative around technology, governance and capital is built. Drawing on mixed methods including content analysis and secondary public interview analysis, the chapter looked at the concurrence or disconnection between the sustainability rhetoric of smart city campaigns and actual DOOH practices. The chapter concluded with a set of strategic guidelines for aligning advertising practices with ecological and social goals of India's urban transformation.

Key Words

Outdoor advertising, sustainability, digital advertising, media ecology

Abbreviations

Digital Out of Home Advertising - DOOH

Out of Home Advertising - OOH

Light Emitting Diode - LED

Digital Technology Acceptance Model -DTAM

Unified Digital Infrastructure -ICT Reference Architecture (UDI-ICTRA)

The Government of India, on the tenth anniversary of its Smart Cities Mission, outlined the achievements made by the cities in different developmental sectors. These tokens of development, taken together, would constitute the smart and sustainable model of the city that is replicated across the country. The distinct ethos of sustainability embedded in the initiative focuses on efficient resource use, green infrastructure and participatory governance.¹ Rather strong in policy, the practice of sustainability remains a “work in progress” in many smart cities.² However, what is relevant to the discussions in this chapter is the idea of the sustainable city, which is a staple in this report and how outdoor digital advertising imparts visual and existential character to the ethos that it typifies.

There are no foundational definitions for the concept of the smart city; the development hypothesis that guides such a mission is oriented according to the sociocultural, historic and demographic needs of each city.³ The Indian Model of smart cities employs two approaches an Area-Based Development framework and a Pan City Project framework, in verticals of Smart Governance, Smart Mobility, Economic Infrastructure, WASH, Vibrant public spaces, Social Infrastructure, Smart Energy and Public-Private Partnership. The policy document released by the Ministry of Urban Development, Government of India, contains an illustrative list of ‘ Smart Solutions’ which are key to the conceptualisation of the Smart City in the Indian context. By its nature, the projects are multilevel, collaborative initiatives.

Locating the discourse on the role of Information and Communication Technology within the policy framework, it was understood that the role of ICT was fashioned in terms of its potential for driving digitalisation and fostering collaboration among stakeholders.⁴ Research on this agenda for ICTs reveals that technology use in urban development, as envisioned in the Smart Cities Mission, has created exclusionary cities⁵ and a deepening of the digital divide.⁶ In this regard, a key observation is that strategies for digitalisation should co-evolve with other assets, capabilities and institutional conditions specific to the area of development.⁷ Framing ICTs as a driver of digitalisation in the process of urban development is coherent with the general notion surrounding the role of science and technology in society. While such a generalist framing has pragmatic benefits, it leaves it to imagination to define how specific technological artefacts can be used for specific roles and purposes.

The ICT discourse in Smart City literature was the point of departure for this chapter. Thinking in this manner prompts the question of how different public media systems that citizens interact with construct the narrative of media use in cities. Scholars of advertising, by exploring mobile and ubiquitous computing technologies in the city, have explained how these technologies fashion the experiences of everyday life in the city, which has already been discussed by early sociologists, too.⁸ The media not only creates affective urban realities for its consumers but also emerges as a political dynamic, creating avenues for relational urban politics.⁹ It is within this general frame of thinking that this article steps into thinking about the sociocultural essence of Digital Out of Home Advertising(DOOH) in Indian Smart Cities. The discussion progresses by trying to answer the questions:

- 1) What are some best practices of digital outdoor advertising that are current in Indian Smart Cities?
- 2) How can the current practices generate a sustainability agenda of Smart Cities, with respect to DOOH?

The chapter unfolds with a review of relevant literature on Digital Out of Home Advertising. It is followed by discussions based on secondary analysis of documents, reports and publicly available interviews of 12 DOOH experts in India. The reason for choosing publicly available interviews is motivated by the researchers' ethic of data minimalism in research, which ensures the sustainability of academic knowledge retrieval and use practices. The chapter then moves on to discuss recent examples of DOOH adoption across select Smart Cities based on a content analysis of news, interviews and public documents. Finally, the insights drawn from the above are channellised into a suggestive framework for a sustainable agenda for DOOH use in smart cities.

I. Sustainability and Urban Visual Strategies: The Case of DOOH

Digital mediascapes generously contribute to the visual and cultural flows in an urban context. The resultant urban visuality is collaboratively constructed by the people, the technologies and the mobilities and practices of each of them. Sustainability is a governing principle in the smart city imaginary, and Out of Home (OOH) digital media strategies are a conveyor of the ethos of sustainability. Digital Out of Home advertising has the capacity to alter the relationships between advertising, the urban environment and the people. The adoption of renewable-powered digital billboards and energy-efficient LED displays reduces the carbon footprint of the advertising medium and also reduces physical waste. Thus, DOOH are not simply a carrier of sustainable messaging, but the technology and the network of practices surrounding it are

themselves on a sustainable footing.¹⁰ As a metaphor for sustainable urban ethics, DOOH integrated with transit corridors, pedestrian zones and civic plazas announces the city's shift to ecological responsibility. In this sense, the message and the medium converge. Clearly, the medium works as one of the many media strategies in a networked city.

The same holds for Indian smart cities, as studies reveal that smart billboards have significantly reduced carbon emissions, even though it remains to be understood how digital advertising alone can lead to climate-sensitive results.¹¹ Testing for climate resilience or the sustainability impact of DOOH systems should be done bearing in mind that the institutional frameworks that come to bear upon the DOOH ecosystem are fragmented and reside in many public and private realms, mainly multilevel governments and advertising businesses. This situation is a multifaceted challenge leading to uncertainty regarding regulatory frameworks and consumer receptivity.^{12a} To elaborate, the regulatory insights are drawn from the Advertising Standards Council of India, the Data Smart Cities Strategy and the Data Maturity and Assessment Framework, Unified Digital Infrastructure -ICT Reference Architecture (UDI-ICTRA) of the Bureau of Indian Standards and the bylaws created by Municipal corporations. The fracturing of the institutional logic creates multiple dependencies for a DOOH agency, which can be rectified to a certain extent with a Digital Technology Acceptance Model(DTAM) for DOOH, an industry standard that can sufficiently increase the adoption of programmatic DOOH in the country.^{12b} A critical gap surfaces in this regard as the regulations deal with size, location, safety and other structural aspects, but not content, usage or programmatic ad platforms.¹³

It is visibly obvious that in India, an absolute transition to digital interactive screens and platforms has not yet occurred. DOOH screens and platforms compete for attention and coexist with other traditional and analogue media strategies in the city.¹⁴ This is true as the indices of the Out of Home (OOH) industry in India show promising levels of growth, with Digital Out of Home Advertising (DOOH) alone gearing up to corner 17 percent of the sector's total revenue shares.¹⁵ Given the proliferation of this media, a multidisciplinary inquiry is much needed to estimate the multifaceted implications of DOOH and its reception amongst people.¹⁶

The review of literature has provided useful thematic categories to broach the subject. The model of Indian urbanism is motivated by the process of adaptive modernisation. Accordingly, the Smart Cities in the country have married smart infrastructure with heritage, informal economies and dense social networks

rather than replacing them with technocratic designs. DOOH strategies are a part of the urban assemblage and reflexively draw on the properties and designs of the institutions and the lived experience of the people that it symbolically and materially interact with.¹⁷

The experience of digital advertising is a key component of the sensory experience of the city. DOOH are affective infrastructures that pierces the visual regimes of urban context.¹⁸ However, they are not isolated cultural forms. Instead, they are sensory and spatial structures that are coterminous with the designs of the smart city. Scholar V. Mehta and S. Pathak comment on the evolving design philosophy of the smart cities, where urban technology, sustainability and socio-spatial justice are treated as interdependent components; the model of resilient urbanism makes sustainability a lived experience.¹⁹ Another case study of digital taxi-top advertising in Mumbai has explained how DOOH has reduced the distance that people have from advertising messaging.²⁰ The discursive media strategies have added an ideological layer to the smart city²¹ · the mediascapes of Bhubaneswar Smart City Park and Sabarmati Riverfront are creating a spatial branding of the place. Despite such notions, the actual potential of the DOOH can be realised only if it can amalgamate with traditional forms of media and other lived media forms. What we are looking at then is a hybrid advertising ecology. a plural public sphere, where digital advertising must connect with other communicative practices for more inclusive urban semiotics.²²

II. The practices and processes of the DOOH industry in India

The theory of media ecosystems conceptualises media as an interconnected and adaptive system where technologies, audience, institutions and culture evolve together. It is through this theoretical lens that the following discussion develops.^{23,24,25} Based on latest market research reports, the Digital Out of Home advertising industry is poised to witness elevated growth fueled by a surge in digital media consumption, increased urbanisation, digitisation of screens and formats, improved measurement and attribution, programmatic buying, increasing third party dependencies, migration of budgets from physical to digital formats and enhanced targeting capabilities and concomitant decline of the legacy media.^{26,27,28} The global sentiments of the DOOH segment have remained positive, with the industry having completely recovered from the pandemic slump and now maintaining a clear upward trajectory. In India, the hotspots for DOOH, which were once concentrated in the metro cities, have now moved to Tier-2 and Tier-3 cities as well. There is a surge in the use of interactive installations, dynamic visuals, programmatic visual content and real-time

data integration. The structural changes are accompanied by changes in culturally sensitive messaging that resonate with different regions. These changes align with the general shifts in the Media and Entertainment Industry in the country, which is growing at a 10% CAGR, from USD 30.8 billion by 2024 to USD 37.2 billion by 2026. A joint study by KPMG International and Outsmart Advertising found that OOH advertising produces the lowest carbon emissions per impression among major media channels, suggesting a strong environmental/sustainability positioning for OOH AND DOOH.

Matching the studies conducted by consulting agencies are the perspectives of industry experts in India. A secondary analysis of 12 interviews of India-based DOOH and ad-tech experts indicated the existence of a DOOH ecosystem. In India, programmatic technologies connect DOOH to the larger media ecosystem by enabling data-driven targeting, automation and measurable engagement.²⁹ This type of technological integration boosts DOOH ecosystems such that they are becoming an *experiential environment* in the digital ecosystem of the smart city.³⁰ The shift from static billboards to a data-driven, environmentally conscious model of outdoor communication is co-produced by capital and technology. An industry expert notes that capital intensity will ensure not just the competitiveness of the medium but also of urban aesthetic integration, emphasising that sustainable infrastructure investment makes DOOH display a public infrastructure of visibility and sustainability.³¹ The problem of fragmented regulation is a structural constraint to creating sustainable advertising infrastructure: DOOH should be considered as *experiential storytelling platforms* capable of transforming urban landscapes into brand-mediated environments, but what hinders the scalability of DOOH are fragmentary regulations and limited analytical capabilities.³² Here, a critical notion of the data imaginaries emerges, much in line with Lefebvre's concept of the production of space, where DOOH technology is situated in the broader social and financial logic of the contemporary city.

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Outdoor advertising expert Alok Jalan, suggests that the DOOH ecosystem must create more experiential formats in a diversity of public places.³⁴ Expert SameBalsara, however, is wary of saying that investment in structural enhancement of DOOH platforms must be accompanied by media mix optimisation and creative strategies to realise the potential of DOOH in public spaces fully.³⁵ DOOH creates brand capital environments within the limits and scopes of urban spatialities, which is both an advantage and a limitation in scaling up DOOH systems.

The high capital expenditure requirement of DOOH is a pain point that limits the scalability of DOOH. Even then, there are benefits to be derived, like contextual and intelligent messaging (using API for weather integration, traffic, AQI) and also emerging touch points like residential DOOH, gated communities, and corporate for future growth.³⁶ A trend captured by the experts is that DOOH is percolating into smaller public avenues and closer to the residential and recreational spaces of citizens. Space, technology and capital have remained critical movers in the adoption of DOOH systems across the country. However, digital fatigue is setting in among the consumers of brand messaging, signalling advertising agencies to move towards static OOH advertisements. This caveat must be considered to review public media strategies and consider DOOH as a part of a hybrid mediated-spatial infrastructure.

Perhaps the most crucial insight has been delivered by Praveen Kumar Vadhera, the CEO of the India Outdoor Advertising Association. According to him, two factors in the DOOH ecosystem can contribute substantially to its maturity: The incorporation of measurement platforms that use real-time user data and the use of recyclable materials to resonate with the rhetoric of sustainability.³⁸ The notion of capturing personal data flows is burgeoning.³⁹ The trend is salient as data infrastructure and connectivity in the cities have been improving; DOOH, in this way, can transition from a mere media inventory to a *placemaking* element in urban life.

The centrality of DOOH media to creating a visually oriented urban public life is a posthuman condition. In the course of its scaling up, DOOH media ecosystems are collating in earlier media dark zones like elevators, malls and other micro environments beyond traditional billboards. Product innovation that triggers location-based behaviours and a merging of DOOH with mobile-based advertising are the next steps in advertising.⁴⁰ Such transformations can cause an upheaval in the public media systems in two ways.⁴¹ Ambient DOOH formats will increasingly integrate motion sensors and cameras to create interactive DOOH experiences. Secondly, these integrations will unlock a 'second-tier' audience that conventional media fail to reach. Even as experts have remained optimistic about the prospects and current practice in the industry, scaling, infrastructure optimisation, and connectivity remain key obstacles in the DOOH media system. Their observations reveal the multidimensional challenges that persist. For them, a pivotal factor is the lack of a media inventory and the absence of industry standards that hinder the DOOH system in India from maturing into a fully integrated Omnichannel audience journey.⁴²

III. Analysing the DOOH ecosystem from a media ecology perspective

A. Technology and programmatic logic

A standing claim in the expert interview is that DOOH's defining transformation is technological: programmatic platforms, data integration and inventory digitisation are envisioned to change the ecosystem in ways that help to align with the mainstream media ecosystem. Advertising practitioners, emphasising programmatic buying and contextually driven information (like location-based, transaction logs-based, and weather/traffic APIs) are suggesting DOOHs as nodes in a media network in which urban DOOHs become part of an information flow that reconfigures social use of media. Despite the positive prognosis, the technological upscaling is a futuristic proposition that can materialise through infrastructure upgrades and standardised measurement practices. From an ecosystem point of view, the consensus hovers around the idea that DOOH is more of a technical system that can offer technological fixes. Technological mediation of this kind can affect urban visibility and mobility as users of the media will experience spatial and temporal distance from the media system. Moreover, the affective and social dimensions of the medium, like creativity and content discovery, become secondary to its technical nature.

B. Aesthetic experiences of DOOH formats

Contemporary scholars of visual culture speak about scopic regimes that are created by visual symbols.⁴³ Foregrounding the power of visuals to make certain ways of looking and perceiving predominant, scopic regimes in cities can create ideas about urban life. A major idea that arose in the experts' statements is the capacity of DOOH to create experiential systems. Their arguments highlight the tendency of DOOH systems to be a *storytelling and placemaking apparatus* rather than mere digitised surfaces, quite in line with the observations made by sociologist Simmel about the sensory experiences in urban spaces that shape the individual's perception of the city. Remediating the experience of the city itself calls into question the power of the medium over its audiences and the resistive power of audiences to frame counter-narratives. In this sense, DOOH formats are active mediators of public perception, both physically and metaphorically. As understood from the interviews, DOOH media works best in strategic locations where more people can see the message and hence more conversion rates for brands. This cultural politics of the media is inherent and easily dismissed. Nevertheless, the creative possibilities of the medium cannot be considered to be absolute, as visibility alone cannot convert into communicative and affective value.

C. Structural Issues

Finally, the interviews coalesce around structural issues: capital intensity, issues of ownership and municipal partnerships and measurement and standardisation of advertising metrics. We see that the DOOH media infrastructure is tightly bound with the institutional logics of the government. Strategic interactions with governments at various levels must create incentive structures and transaction costs that can create an inadvertent policy legacy, too. It is within this structural dimension that the sustainability narrative of the DOOH format becomes evident, with experts commonly attributing sustainability values to the use of recyclable materials, arguing that digital screens can be more efficient than older lit hoardings. However, these claims require scrutiny to assess how the lifecycles of DOOH actually contribute towards the simple yet complex 'Digital is green' rhetoric. Cultural geographer, David Harvey speaks of spatial fixes where capital investment continuously reorganises urban spaces.⁴⁵ Spatial reconstruction, such as that envisioned by DOOH experts, requires regulatory intervention, as commercial intervention alone cannot create progressively data-enabled and context-aware media systems. DOOH emerges as a nexus of technology-capital-governance, leaving us to ponder in a Lefebvrian sense if the nexus alone should play a decisive role in the exemption of citizen and audience demands.

IV. Sustainable Communication and the promises of DOOH

Smart cities across the country have adopted digital solutions to outdoor advertising in dissimilar fashion. Across smart cities chosen-Mumbai, Bengaluru, Kochi, Bhubhaneshwar and Ahmedabad, there is an ecosystem of best practices driven by technology, structural reforms and urban aesthetic management. The following analytical table assembles the best practices in these cities.

It was found that in most of these cases, the outlook and prognosis of the experts aligned with the empirical. There is a steady transition towards a data-driven media environment in the cities analysed. DOOH platforms in the cities are channels for commercial expression as well as civic communication, sustainability awareness and branding. The implementation of campaigns across the cities of Mumbai, Bengaluru, Kochi, Bhubhaneshwar and Ahmedabad signals an expanding ecosystem in which multiple strategies are coming into play. Strategies of technology upgradation are directed towards the adoption of the latest technologies like LED displays, renewable-powered displays and variable messaging. What adds more weft to the technological upgradation is when it is coupled with the strategic positioning of the DOOH

displays. Bus queue shelters, metro stations, and traffic junctions are becoming nodal points for DOOH positioning, owing partly to the traffic and footfall in these regions.

The rhetoric of sustainability, which forms part of the core tenet of Smart Cities, became salient through instances of municipal boards and corporations adopting stricter regulations for the same. Adoption of renewable materials, structural integrity and location-based interventions were key in incorporating measures of sustainability. Moreover, the regional variations in the adoption of DOOH demonstrate how they are being locally contextualised, making it difficult to have a pan Indian agenda for DOOH adoption in the country. This lack of standards impedes the growth of the medium and can be sufficiently buttressed only with standardised governance systems for the medium.⁴⁶ In cities like Mumbai, an obvious sign of this regulatory oversight is the proliferation of illegal OOH.⁴⁷ Collectively, the findings indicate the tensions and synergies between commerce, governance and public communication.⁴⁸ Valuing the close nexus between technology and governance as an indicator of further development in the DOOH advertising format, we can say that the potential for the medium to grow into a sizeable cultural industry in the city is great. It can sufficiently piggyback on the growth trajectory of urban agglomerations into other A, B-1 and B-2 cities in the country. A glaring gap in the various readings by experts and scholars about the DOOH media is related to audience reception and the possibility of creating exclusionary outcomes. While the business discourse exhibits tall claims for context-sensitive and culture-sensitive programming, the real pathways of message reception remain underexplored. The absence of this forethought may create exclusionary urban spaces mediated by DOOH and must be discussed within the ambit of sustainability. Messaging platforms, bylaws and policies for aesthetic enhancement must be considered not merely as tools but as discursive strategies for an inclusive urban semiotics.

Type	Purpose	Usefulness	Transformation
Digital Bus Shelter ⁴⁹ (Bengaluru)	Installed 20 strategically located Digital Bus Shelters at junctions, near malls and key marketplaces.	Maximise visibility during high footfall times , promote sustainable advertising.	Integration of dynamic content, real time content and trigger based advertisements.
Variable Messaging Displays ⁵⁰ (Chennai)	Installed 100 Variable Messaging Displays on high footfall areas for dedicated public service messaging.	Real time public information delivery, reinforce smart city infrastructure , Additional revenue through PPP.	Real time public service messaging, Greater Budgetary allocation by the Greater Chennai Corporation for outdoor advertising.
Digital LED boards ⁵¹ (Chennai)	Intelligent Transport system project to install 616 digital boards in all bus hubs.	To integrate automatic live location data from the city's buses into live data for passengers.	Live data integration, real time tracking.
Vertiq ⁵² (Ahmedabad)	Largest vertical format digital screen with support for 3D and anamorphic content.	Immersive stoytelling.	Increase dynamism of retail environment.
Digital Variable Messaging Integrated system of Intelligent transport and DOOH ⁵³	Installation of DVMS to convert roads into smart roads.	Optimising information delivery.	Optimise road occupany and usage by giving information on route recommendations, Foreign partnership.

Table I. Technology and Programmatic logic

Type	Purpose	Usefulness	Transformation
Greater Bengaluru Governance Act Advertisement Bylaws ⁵⁴ (Bengaluru)	Amongst other regulation the bylaw allows only Electronic screens (LED/LCD) with a minimum of 10 second image transition.	Reduce visual pollution.	Regulatory enforcement.
Digital Kiosks ⁵⁵ (Bubaneswar)	75 outdoor and indoor digital kiosks in various government offices in Bubaneswar.	Offers a range of services including online payment services.	Public service messaging.
Exclusive advertising contracts ⁵⁶ (Ahmedabad)	TimesOOH garnered exclusive advertising contract for 126 digital boards in Ahmedabad.	Low cost of production, high flexibility in campaigns turnaround time.	Multiple audience catchment areas are reached through exclusive contacts.
Long term exclusive contracts ⁵⁷	Signpost India garnered a nine year exclusive contract from Bengaluru Metro Rail Corporation for advertising rights in 67 Namma Metro station.	Dataification of information.	Transform public displays into data led platforms for urban storytelling and brand engagement. Provide Visual Identity through meaningful beautification.
Crabon Neutral-One campaign at a time ⁵⁸	Moving Walls , a DOOH agency in India introduced the first ever carbon-neutral campaign.	Brands will gain transparent measurement of their carbon footprint. Media owners will create inventories of climate-resilient media.	Open pathways for Environmental, social and governance alignment.

Table II. Structural Issues

Type	Purpose	Usefulness	Transformation
Semi-static and fully Dynamic LED Boards ⁵⁹ (Kochi)	Installation of 50 LED billboards to remove illegal and hazardous hoardings.	Reduce illegal and hazardous hoardings.	Increase aesthetic appeal and structural stability.
2024 WWF Earth Hour DOOH Campaign ⁶⁰	Turning off LED screens across 520 DOOH billboards across Delhi, Noida, Mumbai and Bengaluru.	The campaign invites behaviour change (turning off the lights as a direct sustainability message).	Global negotiations of sustainability in advertising.
FlexForward Indian Outdoor Advertising Association and Group M campaign ⁶¹	Aimed to recycle vinyl banners used in OOH sites and switch them to renewable powered DOOH sites, in Delhi and Mumbai.	Meta Sustainability messaging were the medium itself is transforming.	Turning over into sustainable advertising

Table III. Aesthetic Experiences of DOOH Formats and Others

V. Creating a sustainability agenda for Digital Out of Home advertising in India

Any initiation of a sustainability discourse for the DOOH advertising sector should start with an ecosystem approach. Regarding the DOOH ecosystem in India, it has been sufficiently stated that any enhancement to the current system must consider the nexus of technology-capital-governance that comes to bear upon it. To this end, any sustainability policy for DOOH must consider the following:

1. Content cultures in the DOOH medium must promote messaging that directly delivers citizen-centric knowledge on sustainable practices in cities, offices, road and other public environments.
2. Assume sustainability as a technoprogressive agenda in the industry that can accelerate technological adoption without compromising on social and cultural growth- advertising companies must adhere to genuine green marketing strategies and avoid greenwashing.
3. Sustainability measurement of DOOH media as a key measurement metric- multilevel governments and companies must disclose the environmental impacts of their DOOH initiatives.
4. Focusing on product and process design for the adoption of sustainable technologies; design standards and business process standards must ensure key environmental sensitivity.

5. Regulatory uniformity at different levels of government for DOOH- the regulations and laws that should govern the DOOH system must be adaptive and work well with regulations and laws at other levels and regions.
6. Aesthetics of the environment should not be compromised when installing DOOH. Clutter-free skylines and roadsides must be prioritised equally.
7. Installation of DOOH media systems must not put at risk the lives and livelihoods of vulnerable people. Ecological and sociological vulnerability mapping must be made a prerequisite for installing DOOH systems.
8. Area-based development and citizen information delivery must be priorities when setting up DOOH ecosystems. Even while creating brand capital environments, a percentage of display time and content should be set aside for citizen-centric public policy messaging.
9. An agenda for the DOOH media system must consider an ecosystem view of media. It should consider the effects on and feedback from citizens, businesses, local self-governments, and ecological sensitivity when proposing the agenda.

V. The future of DOOH media in India

Indian cities are a key site where sociotechnical and cultural systems collide with fervour. The social capital of the urban publics is, as never before, being directed by the media. With the mediation of a variety of public and private media, urban spaces are becoming spheres of contestation between various ideological organisations. It is rather simplistic to consider DOOH systems as just other media imaginary created in an ethos of neoliberal capitalism. But such a reductionist view would neglect the ubiquity of digital advertising platforms that are built all around us and that capture and direct our attention. DOOH media has become part of our everyday urban rituals; it is crucial, therefore, to give it the critical gaze that it deserves.

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